

Emotions vs. Biological Processes: Time Perception Edition

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Literature Review

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Abstract

This literature review will investigate whether emotional states or neural timing mechanisms have a more significant influence on how quickly we perceive time to pass. This will be accomplished by analyzing evidence from various studies grounded in models such as the pacemaker-accumulator theory and the time-emotion paradox theory. These evaluations suggest that emotional arousal has a more substantial impact on how fast we perceive time, as there is a more noticeable shift in time perception in studies involving emotional arousal compared to the change seen in studies on the standard biological timing processes. Overall, these findings suggest that emotional arousal plays an important role in shaping how individuals perceive the passing of time.

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Are our memories accurate? According to Johan Norberg, author of *False Nostalgia* in *Reason Magazine*, people tend to romanticize the past. The author uses an example from when Jason Feiffer asked when America was at its best on the podcast *Build for Tomorrow*; the most popular answer was the 1950s. However, when scholars from then were asked if this was true, they responded that it wasn't because "...people were worried about race and class and the impact of television, and the very real threat of instant nuclear annihilation." (Norberg, 2022, para. 13). This shows how our perception can be skewed based on the context. Seph Lawless illustrates this through his photographs of urban decay and destruction, which can also be interpreted differently by each person.

For example, his photograph of an abandoned mall can be analyzed to show some of the negative effects of technology, such as how it can decrease the amount of time people spend outside or with one another. However, a different analysis could be that someone just sees an abandoned mall. It all depends on the way the person looks at it, their emotions, and how they perceive it. This relates to how our perception is influenced by our emotions, thus showing that our perception of time is dependent on the situation, which can, in turn, influence our emotions and how we perceive how much time has passed.

This influenced the research question: Do emotions or biological processes in the brain have a more significant influence on how fast we perceive time to go by? Based on the evidence, emotions have a more significant influence on how fast time is perceived to go by, which can be seen in theories such as the pacemaker theory or the time-emotion paradox theory. This report will discuss a few different theories and how they provide evidence for the concept that emotions have a more significant influence on how fast we perceive time to go by.

Methods

This literature review is a narrative review and was conducted using databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, the National Institute of Health, and JSTOR to locate sources within the date range of 2005-2025. Some keywords that were used are “time perception”, “Pacemaker-Accumulator Theory”, “Internal Clock”, “Neural Models”, “Time-Emotion Paradox”, “emotional arousal”, “Modular Model”, “Attentional Gate Model”, just to name a few. Types of sources used included theoretical papers, experimental studies, neuroscience reviews, psychological reviews, and initial foundational articles drawn from a collection of expert, peer-reviewed sources assembled for an academic research course. Sources were required to be peer-reviewed, relate to time perception, and/or address emotional and biological mechanisms in time perception, and be based on academic research. Sources were excluded if they were non-English, non-academic, not peer-reviewed, or overall untrustworthy. A total of 13 sources were analyzed qualitatively through theoretical comparison, pattern identification across observational sources, and juxtaposition between emotional and biological influences on chronoception.

Results

The following section summarizes the relationship between emotions, biology, and time perception. Based on the evidence, emotions are seen to have a more significant influence on how fast time is perceived to go by, which can be seen in theories such as the pacemaker theory, where a pacemaker represents how much time went by, or by the time-emotion paradox theory of emotions affecting our attention rather than the internal clock itself.

Emotional Influence: Pacemaker Theory

According to a study by neuroresearchers Mella et al. (2010), the pacemaker theory states that humans have a type of pacemaker (internal clock) that creates pulses, and the number of pulses over a given amount of time represents the amount of time that one perceives has passed. The source states, “Various studies have shown that humans and other animals can estimate time accurately in the millisecond to minutes range. (Angrilli et al., 1997, Droit-Volet et al., 2004, Noulhiane et al., 2007, Tipples, 2008)” (Mella, pg. 2). However, this ability varies heavily on the context in which one is, because the context one is in can affect one’s emotion, and their emotions can affect the amount of pulses the pacemaker makes. For example, the stronger the emotion, the faster the pacemaker will pulse and the more pulses one will experience. This explains why when someone is in anticipation, they feel that more time has passed by, because there are more pulses in the same amount of time. Vice versa, when someone is experiencing an emotion that isn’t as intense as excitement, such as boredom or ennui, they will feel that time is passing by at a slower pace because the pacemaker is slowing down, meaning fewer pulses during the same period. If someone is experiencing a neutral emotion, the pacemaker will go at a steady pace, and time will be perceived at a more “standard” rate.

Biological Influence: The Internal Clock and Neural Models

However, emotions aren't the only factors that influence time perception; biological processes also play a role. The idea is that the brain has an internal clock that works with the nervous system to generate ticks that measure time. There are many different scientists with different theories of how the internal clock works and the role different parts of the brain play in time perception. For example, according to a study done by neuroscience researchers Cope et al. (2013), "Recent studies demonstrate the cerebellum to be involved in absolute, duration-based timing, but not in relative timing based on a regular beat" (Cope et al., 2013, pg. 1). In simpler terms the study is stating that the cerebellum is in charge of absolute timing such as how long an event lasts, and later states that the basal ganglia is in charge of relative timing also known as beats and rhythms. Now, there are different theories on how the different parts of the brain, specifically, the cerebellum and basal ganglia, work together to facilitate time perception.

The first theory is called the modular model. Psychology and neuroscience researchers Ivry and Schlerf (2008) describe the modular model as "specializations, unique to particular neural structures, that provide a functional chronotopy that is recruited across diverse task domains" (Ivry & Schlerf, 2008). This quote states that each compartment of the brain involved in time perception, in this instance, the basal ganglia and cerebellum, has a different function, and none have the same function. The second theory being discussed is called the unified model, as defined by Cope et al. (2013), "these neural modules are not functionally independent but part of an integrated system, as elaborated in the hypothesised unified model of time perception (Meck, 2005, Teki et al., 2012)" (Cope et al., 2013, pg. 1). This theory, as defined in the quotation, is when the different compartments of the brain work together as a system and share

functions or have multiple functions. For instance, this theory supports the idea that the Basal Ganglia plays a role in both relative and absolute timing.

Integrated Perspective: The Time-Emotion Paradox

Going back to how emotions influence time perception: the time-emotion paradox. As described by a review published in the *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, “For example, the passage of time seems to vary depending on whether the subject is in an unpleasant or pleasant context. It drags when being criticized by the boss, but flies by when discussing with our friends. That is the time–emotion paradox: why, given that we possess a sophisticated time measurement mechanism, are we so inaccurate in our temporal judgements when experiencing emotions?” (Droit-Volet et al., 2009, pg. 1). Simply explaining that the time-emotion paradox is that despite the fact humans have the ability to accurately estimate how much time has gone by, time perception is distorted by one’s emotional state, environment, and attention, to name a few factors. It combines different theories and ideas to form a concept that explains how humans do have an internal clock, but it is heavily influenced by external factors. A few examples of the different theories it combines are the pacemaker theory, attentional gate model (our emotions affect our focus on time and how much time we feel passed by), internal clock model, and theories of the different parts of the brain’s function in time perception (basal ganglia and cerebellum).

Discussion

Now, while these theories are compelling, one might note that the internal clock model is similar to the pacemaker theory, and while they would be technically correct in their observation, there are some important differences between the two. The internal clock model is solely biological with no emotional influences, whereas the pacemaker theory has an emotional influence, making it a more realistic and compelling argument. Theories on the biological processes behind time perception tend to have fixed processes, which aren't very realistic. The brain is complex, with numerous factors to consider and acknowledge; for example, emotions. While biological processes may provide the structure for time perception, emotions have a greater impact on time perception. A review written by psychological and neuroscience researchers, Matthews and Meck (2014), highlights some of the limitations of viewing time perception through a biological lens "...we focus on three pieces of 'bad news' for time perception research: temporal perception is highly labile across changes in experimental context and task; there are pronounced individual differences not just in overall performance but in the use of different timing strategies and the effect of key variables; and laboratory studies typically bear little relation to timing in the 'real world'" (Matthews & Meck, 2014, pg. 1). The author reasons that theories researched in labs may show a way of how people experience time, but they don't show how people experience time in the real world, in real situations, and not just in a controlled environment. They also argue that time perception changes depending on the task and situation an individual is in, which, again, is a limitation of ideas researched in labs or controlled environments.

Now, while discussing biological processes, it was specified that the internal clock was strictly biological and not influenced by emotions, which is what made it different from the

pacemaker theory. However, when discussing a different theory, the time-emotion paradox, the internal clock is very much influenced by emotions. This illustrates the extensive research and complexity of this topic, and the research that needs to be done to address this complexity. Well, even though this report argues that emotions are the most influential factor in the way we perceive time, there are still so many theories out there that agree, disagree, and combine theories together. This brings back an earlier topic that it's all based on an individual's perception, emotions, situation, and many other factors.

Conclusion

In conclusion, emotions have a more significant influence on how fast we perceive time to go by, which can be seen in theories such as the pacemaker theory, where a pacemaker represents how much time went by, or by the time-emotion paradox theory of emotions affecting our attention rather than the internal clock itself. As mentioned, many biological processes and theories of biological processes explain how we tell time, however, the way in which many of those theories were studied and researched have several limitations to them. There are not only many theories on biological processes in the brain, but there are also a multitude of theories on time perception itself. This is what makes this topic so complex and controversial. You don't know the right answer, yet there isn't exactly a "right" or "wrong" answer; there are just theories and one's position based on those theories. After reviewing all the evidence thus far, one can conclude that emotions have a more significant influence on how we perceive time.

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